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Assessment of Production Planning Strategies and Cost Minimization Effectiveness of Food and Beverage Companies in South-South Nigeria

Monday Peter¹ & Wosowei, C. Elizabeth²

^{1,2}Department of Economics

Isaac Jasper Boro College of Education, Sagbama, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

¹pmoday316@gmail.com; ²julizpre@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study examined the assessment of production planning strategies and cost minimization effectiveness of food and beverage companies in south-south Nigeria. The descriptive survey research design was employed in this study. The population of the study thus, involved senior management and those whose job description gives them a direct link to production and inventory management. The target population was 4839 respondents. The sample size for this study is 106 respondents. Purposive sampling technique was used to sample the firms and the respondents for the study. This study made use of primary data precisely. The study developed an instrument titled “Assessment of Production Planning Strategies and Cost Minimization Effectiveness of Food and Beverage Companies” (APPSCMEFBC). The data obtained from the study was analysed using simple mean and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The findings obtained from research question 1, table 1 showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 had a mean value of 3.44, 3.22, 3.55 and 3.12 respectively. The findings obtained from research question 2, table 2 showed that item 5 and 6 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 5 and 6 had a mean value of 3.78 and 3.67 respectively. The findings obtained from research question 3, table 3 showed that item 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 all had a mean value of 3.23, 3.45, 3.89, 3.15, 3.88 and 3.67 respectively. The findings obtained from research question 4, table 4 showed that item 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17 had a mean value of 3.11, 3.34, 3.10, 3.34 and 3.90 respectively. The findings obtained from research question 5, table 5 showed that item 18, 19, 20 and 21 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 18, 19, 20 and 21 had a mean value of 3.21, 3.78, 3.56 and 3.33 respectively. Further findings obtained from the study showed that the r-calculated value of 5.49 is greater than r-tabulated value of 0.878 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, it would be stated that there is significant correlation between chase production strategy and make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy on cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South. Based on the findings obtained from the study, it was recommended amongst others that most medium size industries should adopt the production strategy that creates effective labour and minimize cost in industries.

Keywords: Assessment, Production, Planning, Strategies, Cost, Minimization, Effectiveness Food, Beverage and Companies

INTRODUCTION

The country's processed food industry is expected to grow by several tens of billions of dollars by 2050 (Flanders investment & trade, 2020). Due to the recent economic meltdown, consumers are looking to save as much money as possible. This has raised concerns in the food processing companies, causing them to become more innovative in order to decrease the cost of goods, attract more customers and increase profit margins. Furthermore, rising costs of factors of production constitute the major problem to this industry as well. Since inflation and commodity prices went up in the past years, food companies have had to increase prices of the final product as well. This is forcing the companies to look inwards and find ways of minimizing cost by reviewing their production planning strategies and processes. New approaches to production planning are being explored by the food and beverage industries. Production planning has become an essential component of the overall production process in the business environment.

Production planning is the act of developing a guide for the design and production of a given product or service (Lutkevich, 2018). It is the planning and allocation of raw materials, workers, and workstations to fulfill manufacturing orders in time. Production planning aims at fixing production goals and to estimate the resources which are required to achieve these goals. It prepares a detailed plan for achieving the production goals economically, efficiently and in time. It forecasts each step in the production process. It forecasts the problems, which may arise in the production process and tries to remove these problems. It attempts to remove the causes of wastage.

Manufacturing companies have identified the need to orientate their logistics strategies towards time, allowing them to increase supply chain efficiency while gaining a competitive advantage. The reason for these changes is, among other things, external pressure to shorten the order cycle, reduce its volatility, and deliver the order at the time and place required by the customer or the end-user of the product. This can be done by improving the ability to manage and control information in the supply chain as well as inside and outside the organization. Companies increase their sensitivity to customer needs, trying to answer them without interruption, and at the same time reduce inventories throughout the supply chain (Coyle, Bardi and Langley, 2002).

Based on Chopra and Meindl, (2010), a key element affecting the supply chain efficiency is a good choice of the four driven supply chain performance model that supports the overall supply chain strategy. The supply chain efficiency drivers are the following: inventories, information, equipment, and transportation. Companies ultimately want to reduce costs relative to increase in production. Cost minimization is the task of trying to reduce costs. Cost minimization is the process of using resources in the most effective way so that expenses are reduced. It is a financial strategy that seeks to achieve the most cost-effective way of delivering goods and services to the required level of quality (Board, 2021). According to Board (2021), cost minimization is a basic rule used by producers to determine what mix of labour and capital produces output at the lowest cost. In other words, it implies what the most cost-effective method of delivering goods and services would be while maintaining a desired level of quality. These inputs are increasingly becoming costly, so firms must be smart about how they use labour, capital and other inputs to achieve a certain level of output. The goal of any profit maximizing firm is to produce any level of output at the minimum cost. In many businesses, there are a number of ways in which a particular quantity of output can get created. This entails the use of production planning strategies.

Utilizing specific strategies for production planning can boost efficiency, reduce waste, reduce cost, and ultimately improve the overall production process. Production planning strategy is a strategy that enables manufacturers to achieve maximum efficiency in the manufacturing or production of goods intended for sale. These manufacturing production strategies offer different approaches to handling inventory control, overhead, customization and production speed, while providing various levels of savings in labour costs (Gordon, 2022). The main strategies used in production planning are the chase strategy, level production, make-to-stock, and assemble to order.

A single manufacturing facility produces the products one at a time, and successive manufacturing times for each product comprise a sequence of general random variables. Different products may have different manufacturing-time distributions. Demands for the products are independent Poisson processes with

different arrival rates. The costs of managing the production inventory system are stationary and include inventory holding and backordering costs. Although the form of the optimal production inventory policy for this system has not been established, a base-stock (order-up-to) inventory policy has been shown to be optimal in a similar system under periodic review. Also, the base-stock inventory policy has commonly been used in previous work analysing other aspects of systems similar to the one considered here. For these reasons we adopt a base-stock inventory policy for our system.

Furthermore, the additional information and coordination required at the production facility by dynamic scheduling rules may counter the inventory savings over the FCFS rule. As a result and given that FCFS is common in practice, we will adopt FCFS as the scheduling rule for our system.

Statement of the Problem

The food and beverage industry is faced with a myriad of changes, driving reforms and altering production planning to meet with changing consumer demands, technological advancements and regulatory requirements. Traditional companies are battling new entrants into the market in the form of e-commerce and those in the informal sector, affecting earnings and production. Being a consumer driven industry, changes in consumer preferences, buying behaviours and purchasing power are all factors that are affecting supplies and production. Other challenges are cost based and are related to the internal operations of the company. Food and beverage companies are most likely dealing with high inventory costs, erratic demands by consumers and growing capital costs, forcing companies to review their production processes. Costs are going up, from cost of raw materials, foreign exchange and supply bottlenecks. Reviewing production planning strategies has become inevitable for food and beverage companies in the light of rising costs. As companies look to minimize costs some questions arise: Is it possible that the application of different production planning strategies could help their cost minimization effectiveness? What methods of production planning could be best suitable for the food and beverage industry for cost minimization? These are the questions that gave rise to this study. Hence, the researcher intends to ascertain if production planning strategies effect the cost minimization of food and beverage companies in south-south Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to assess the relationship between production planning strategies and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between chase production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South.
2. Examine the relationship between make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South.
3. Determine the relationship between level production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South.
4. Assess the relationship between assemble-to-order (ATO) production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South.
5. Determine the relationship between capacity planning production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between chase production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South?
2. What is the relationship between make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South?
3. What is the relationship between level production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South?
4. What is the relationship between assemble-to-order (ATO) production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South?
5. What is the relationship between capacity planning production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South?

Hypothesis

The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

There is no significant correlation between chase production strategy and make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy on cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The food and beverage industry in Nigeria

The food and beverage industry encapsulates all firms or organizations that are into processing, packaging and distributing raw food materials: it includes prepared, fresh, and packaged foods as well as alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages. In fact, any product that is made for human consumption apart from pharmaceutical ones are classified under the food and beverage industry. According to a report by Coleman (2018), the food and beverage industry is made of two major segments: the production segment and the distribution (of edible goods) segment. The production segment is concerned with processing of raw food materials like meat, cheese, and the making of alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages, and packaged foods. The distribution segment is charged with transporting finished goods to the final consumer. The food and beverage industry is a major driver of the economy of Nigeria. According to data from the World Trade Organisation, Nigeria ranks as the largest foodstuff market in Africa, with both significant investment in the local industry and a high level of imports.

According to FAOSTAT, Nigeria has 70.8 million hectares of agricultural land, of which 37m ha is arable. The arable land comprises small, medium and large levels of farming in which the smallholders dominate the agricultural and livestock production landscape through their cultivation of (mainly) rice and cassava. In addition to these commodities, the smallholders also keep cattle, small ruminants, and poultry. With almost 100 million people actively involved in subsistence farming and contributing 21% of the GDP, it can be inferred that Nigeria is, quintessentially, an agrarian economy that slowly develops food manufacturing and service sectors.

Crop production in Nigeria accounts for 88% of the total agricultural industry size. It is the primary driver of agrarian sector output, contributing an average of 90% to the overall agricultural sector output between 2012 and 2018, and growing at a CAGR of 3.6% over the same period. Crop production includes the production of cash crops (cocoa, rubber, etc.) and staple foods (Rice, Maize and Cassava) in a landmass of 82.0 million hectares out of the total landmass of 92.4 million hectares. Nigeria is the largest producer of cassava, yam and cowpea in the world. Other significant crops include groundnut, palm oil and cocoa. With regards to specific crop production in the varying regions of the country, grains such as millet and wheat are found in the Northern part of the country while cassava, yam, and rice are popular in the Southern and South Western parts of Nigeria.

Livestock development is an essential component of Nigerian agriculture with huge economic potential. About 60% of the livestock population is found in the country's semi-arid zone and mostly managed by pastoralists. In addition, livestock represents around 1.7% of the national GDP and about 9% to agricultural value-added. Recent estimates indicate that Nigeria's national herd comprises 18.4 million cattle, 43.4 million sheep, 76 million goats, and 180 million poultry. Domestic production of livestock is considered far below the needs of the country.

Production Planning Strategy

Production planning is a guideline for manufacturers in carrying out the production process. It deals with basic concepts of what to produce when to produce, how much to produce, and so on. Production planning is long-term and aims to ensure high-quality resources are always available during the process (Kelber, 2020). A production plan is a tool that companies can use to develop a strategy for meeting forecasted demands while minimizing costs. An effective production plan also enables companies to reduce the amount of stored inventory they hold and make the best use of their manufacturing plant space and equipment.

Effective scheduling and planning can save costs, streamline processes, optimize equipment utilization, and ensure timeliness in meeting consumer needs. Thus, it is important for manufacturers to optimize their production planning. (Kanya, 2022). Production planning and scheduling entails a clear definition of

starting and finishing time frames and allocation of resources to each task within the main job: It is restricted by many constraints like resources and tasks. Production planning is essentially the short-term execution plan to execute a production.

Production planning involves making prior decisions on how to carry out a certain strategy in a business which involves: the material to produce, the period of production, and the exact location to carry out the production process. A well designed plan with good understanding of the future outcomes helps to avoid failure due to uncertainties. Production planning aims at looking ahead and estimating the type of resources required in an organization and then coming up with the proper arrangements which enables attainment of the set production targets in the proposed plan (MBA Knowledge Base, 2011). Production planning strategy on the other hand, involves coming up with ways and means of achieving the above objectives. The main strategies used in production planning are the chase strategy, level production, make-to-stock production and assemble to order.

Cost minimization

A firms' problem is maximizing profit by choosing optimal quantities of inputs to employ and output to produce. This falls under the concept of cost maximization. Cost minimization is the task of trying to reduce costs. It is the process of using resources in the most effective way so that expenses are reduced. Cost minimization is the rule in which producers seek to calculate the right balance between two inputs in order to have the most cost-effective productivity. Cost minimization as defined by (Patrick 2019) is the process of reducing expenditures on unnecessary or inefficient processes. These changes in spending can be slight or drastic, but any level of reduction in costs will likely have a dramatic effect on maximizing profits. Cost minimization strategy and efforts can occur in any area of a business including manufacturing, freight and packaging, finance and accounting, human resources, legal, marketing, direct selling, and more. The goal of cost minimization strategy is to identify the area(s) in which a business can effectively reduce costs that will have the most beneficial effect on maximizing profits.

Cost minimization is a necessary condition for profit maximization in competitive markets. By analyzing operations and other areas of a business and stripping down to the most efficient, "lean and mean" processes, organizations are able to identify problem areas, change unproductive methods, streamline procedures and ultimately reduce costs significantly (Patrick, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey research design was employed in this study. The population of the study thus, involved senior management and those whose job description gives them a direct link to production and inventory management. The target population was 4839 respondents. The sample size for this study is 106 respondents. Purposive sampling technique was used to sample the firms and the respondents for the study. This study made use of primary data precisely. The study developed an instrument titled "Assessment of Production Planning Strategies and Cost Minimization Effectiveness of Food and Beverage Companies" (APPSCMEFBC). The instrument is a likert scale questionnaire items consisting of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). The response items were weighed as 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The study made use of questionnaires to gather data for the study. The researcher through the aid of research assistants administers the questionnaire to the respondents. The data obtained from the study was analysed using simple mean and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient.

DATA ANALYSIS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between chase production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South?*

Table 1: Relationship between chase production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
1	Labour cost enhances cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South	3.44	Accept
2	Effective turn over enhances cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South	3.22	Accept
3	High cost of extra delivery from supply enhances cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South	3.55	Accept
4	Quality of product enhances cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South	3.12	Accept
	Total	13.33	

The findings obtained from research question 1, table 1 showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 had a mean value of 3.44, 3.22, 3.55 and 3.12 respectively. This implies that labour cost, effective turn over, high cost of extra delivery from supply and quality of product enhances cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South?*

Table 2: Relationship between make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
5	Make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy enhances time management and reduces cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South?	3.78	Accept
6	Make-to-stock (MTS) initiates inventory supply control to minimize cost in production of food and beverages.	3.67	Accept
	Total	7.45	

The findings obtained from research question 2, table 2 showed that item 5 and 6 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 5 and 6 had a mean value of 3.78 and 3.67 respectively. This implies that make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy enhances time management and initiates inventory supply control to minimize cost in production of food and beverages.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between level production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South?*

Table 3: Relationship between level production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
7	The quantity of product supplied affects the rate of consumption negatively.	3.23	Accept
8	Bigger amount of production aid corporation attain economies of scale	3.45	Accept
9	Level of production plan can assist a company in effectively managing its personnel.	3.89	Accept
10	Level of production gives room for smoothness and efficiency	3.15	Accept
11	Level of production can company in cost reduction	3.88	Accept
12	The buyer confidence is eroded when products a product is not available to fill request.	3.67	Accept
	Total	21.27	

The findings obtained from research question 3, table 3 showed that item 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 all had a mean value of 3.23, 3.45, 3.89, 3.15, 3.88 and 3.67 respectively. This implies that the quantity of product supplied affects the rate of consumption negatively, bigger amount of production Aid Corporation attain economies of scale, level of production plan can assist a company in effectively managing its personnel, level of production gives room for smoothness and efficiency, level of production can company in cost reduction and the buyer confidence is eroded when products a product is not available to fill request.

Research Question 4: *What is the relationship between assemble-to-order (ATO) production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South?*

Table 4: Relationship between assemble-to-order (ATO) production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
13	Assemble to Order improves production supply chain to meet customers demand in food and beverage companies	3.11	Accept
14	ATO minimizes production cost by making product readily available to consumers	3.34	Accept
15	ATO improves the quality of delivery service to customers in food and beverage companies	3.10	Accept
16	ATO creates value for products to maintain customer's interest and minimize cost.	3.45	Accept
17	ATO creates strong sense of customers' reliability and minimal cost of duty in supply of food and beverages.	3.90	Accept
	Total	16.90	

The findings obtained from research question 4, table 4 showed that item 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17 had a mean value of 3.11, 3.34, 3.10, 3.34 and 3.90 respectively. This implies that Assemble to Order improves production supply chain to meet customers demand, minimizes production cost by making product readily available to consumers, improves the quality of delivery service to customers, creates value for products to maintain customer's interest and creates strong sense of customers' reliability and minimal cost of duty in food and beverage companies.

Research Question 5: *What is the relationship between capacity planning production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South?*

Table 5: Relationship between capacity planning production strategy and cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	DECISION
18	Lead strategy enhances production and cost minimization of food and beverage companies	3.21	Accept
19	Lag strategy gives room for growth and cost minimization of food and beverage companies.	3.78	Accept
20	Match strategy improves production and cost minimization of food and beverage companies	3.56	Accept
21	Adjustment strategy creates flexible approach in problem solving and cost minimization of food and beverage companies	3.33	Accept
	Total	13.88	

The findings obtained from research question 5, table 5 showed that item 18, 19, 20 and 21 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 18, 19, 20 and 21 had a mean value of 3.21, 3.78, 3.56 and 3.33 respectively. This implies that lead strategy enhances production and cost minimization of food and beverage companies, lag strategy gives room for growth and cost minimization of food and beverage companies, match strategy improves production and cost minimization of food and

beverage companies and adjustment strategy creates flexible approach in problem solving and cost minimization of food and beverage companies.

Hypothesis

There is no significant correlation between chase production strategy and make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy on cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South.

Table 6: Correlation between chase production strategy and make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy on cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South

S/N	Chase production strategy (X)	make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy (Y)	XY	X ²	Y ²
1	3.44	3.78	13.00	11.83	14.29
2	3.22	3.67	11.82	10.37	13.47
3	3.55		3.55	12.60	
4	3.12		3.12	9.73	
	13.33	7.45	31.49	44.53	27.76

The r-calculated value of 5.49 is greater than r-tabulated value of 0.878 at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the null hypothesis was rejected based on the decision rule. Therefore, it would be stated that there is no significant correlation between chase production strategy and make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy on cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings obtained from research question 1, table 1 showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 1, 2, 3 and 4 had a mean value of 3.44, 3.22, 3.55 and 3.12 respectively. This implies that labour cost, effective turn over, high cost of extra delivery from supply and quality of product enhances cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South. This is in line with the view of Gordon, (2022) that opined that chase production strategy creates effective labour and minimize cost in industries.

The findings obtained from research question 2, table 2 showed that item 5 and 6 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 5 and 6 had a mean value of 3.78 and 3.67 respectively. This implies that make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy enhances time management and initiates inventory supply control to minimize cost in production of food and beverages. Kelber, (2020) said that make-to-stock production boast food production and beverages.

The findings obtained from research question 3, table 3 showed that item 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 all had a mean value of 3.23, 3.45, 3.89, 3.15, 3.88 and 3.67 respectively. This implies that the quantity of product supplied affects the rate of consumption negatively, bigger amount of production Aid Corporation attain economies of scale, level of production plan can assist a company in effectively managing its personnel, level of production gives room for smoothness and efficiency, level of production can company in cost reduction and the buyer confidence is eroded when products a product is not available to fill request. Lutkevich, (2018) opined that the level of production reduces industrial cost.

The findings obtained from research question 4, table 4 showed that item 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17 had a mean value of 3.11, 3.34, 3.10, 3.34 and 3.90 respectively. This implies that Assemble to Order improves production supply chain to meet customers demand, minimizes production cost by making product readily available to consumers, improves the quality of delivery service to customers, creates value for products to maintain customer’s interest and creates strong sense of customers’ reliability and minimal cost of duty in food and beverage companies. Flanders investment & trade (2020) states that assembly-to-order aids in organising production.

The findings obtained from research question 5, table 5 showed that item 18, 19, 20 and 21 were all accepted to the various questions. The study also showed that item 18, 19, 20 and 21 had a mean value of

3.21, 3.78, 3.56 and 3.33 respectively. This implies that lead strategy enhances production and cost minimization of food and beverage companies, lag strategy gives room for growth and cost minimization of food and beverage companies, match strategy improves production and cost minimization of food and beverage companies and adjustment strategy creates flexible approach in problem solving and cost minimization of food and beverage companies. Coleman, (2000) opined that production strategy minimizes loss in food and beverage companies.

The r-calculated value of 5.49 is greater than r-tabulated value of 0.878 at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the null hypothesis was rejected based on the decision rule. Therefore, it would be stated that there is significant correlation between chase production strategy and make-to-stock (MTS) production strategy on cost minimization of food and beverage companies in South South. Lutkevich, (2018) states that make-to-stock and chase production both enhances production capacity of the industries.

CONCLUSION

In all, the chase production strategy creates effective labour and minimize cost in industries, make-to-stock production boost food production and beverages, the level of production reduces industrial cost, assembly-to-order aids in organising production, production strategy minimizes loss in food and beverage companies and make-to-stock and chase production both enhances production capacity of the industries.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings obtained from the study, it was recommended that:

1. Most medium size industries should adopt the production strategy to creates effective labour and minimize cost in industries
2. Industries should apply make-to-stock production system to boost food production and beverages
3. Small organisation should apply assembly-to-order aids in organising production.
4. Most small medium enterprise should undergo training on production strategy to minimize loss in food and beverage companies.

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